

Peer Review Report

PEER REVIEW REPORT FOR:

Nadir, A. M. Junior, Alberton, A., Borba, J. A., & Saath, K. C. O. (2026). The effects of expansionary fiscal policy on macroeconomic development: A study on tax competition in an emerging market. *BAR-Brazilian Administration Review*, 23(1), e250057. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1807-7692bar2026250057>

HOW TO CITE THIS PEER REVIEW REPORT:

Nadir, A. M. Junior, Alberton, A., Borba, J. A., Saath, K. C. O., & Torres, M. (2026). Peer review report for: The effects of expansionary fiscal policy on macroeconomic development: A study on tax competition in an emerging market. *Brazilian Administration Review*. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18484311>

REVIEWERS:

- Miguel Torres (University of Kent, Kent Business School, United Kingdom)
The other reviewers did not authorize the disclosure of his/her reports

ROUND 1

Reviewer 1 report

Reviewer 1 for this round chose not to disclose his/her review report.

Authors' Response

The authors' responses to the comments of Reviewer 1 for this round were omitted from this report, since the reviewer did not authorize the disclosure of his/her reports.

Reviewer 2 report

Reviewer: Miguel Torres

Date review returned: May 10, 2025

Recommendation: Major revision

Comments to the authors

This is a great and necessary work that exposes the trade-offs of expansionary fiscal policy in emerging markets, where budgetary stimulus can exacerbate inflationary pressures and currency volatility. This is the kind of paper that gets a grip on reality.

In July 2024, the Brazilian central bank director highlighted concerns about persistent expansionary fiscal policy, noting its pressure on the exchange rate and monetary policy, complicating efforts to disinflate the economy. Brazil's government has pursued increased public spending to stimulate growth, raising concerns about long-term fiscal sustainability. Thus, policymakers are unsure what to do, and you can help them. Therefore, the first route for improvement is to target policymakers and explain to them what to do with the results.

In more detail,

1. Enhance Presentation and Synthesis. Streamline the IRF discussion by synthesising findings into a cohesive narrative addressing the research objective. Utilise visual aids (e.g., summary tables or consolidated IRF graphs) to improve clarity. Minimise repetition in the literature review by concentrating on studies most relevant to the research question and linking them to the study's hypotheses. Ensure accessibility for non-specialist readers by clarifying technical terms (e.g., Cholesky decomposition, IRF) and providing intuitive interpretations of results.

2. Literature is well-revised to support the examination of the dynamic impacts of fiscal policy, showing how government spending increases and tax cuts stimulate economic activity in the short term you included Blanchard, O., & Perotti, R. (2002), I agree, but to support empirical evidence on the effectiveness of expansionary fiscal policy in boosting economic output, particularly during recessions. You must consider and discuss your results against: "Auerbach, A. J., & Gorodnichenko, Y. (2012). Measuring the output responses to fiscal policy. *American Economic Journal: Economic Policy*, 4(2), 1-27."

3. Expansionary Fiscal Policy (EFP) refers to government measures designed to stimulate economic activity by increasing aggregate demand, typically through higher public spending, tax reductions, or a combination of both. It is often employed during economic downturns or recessions to stimulate employment, increase income, and promote growth. The policy aims to close output gaps and stabilise economies by injecting money into the system, encouraging consumption and investment. Consider these ideas to make your introduction more straightforward for the reader.

4. Your study will be stronger if you expand the inclusion of variables and address some data limitations. Incorporate additional macroeconomic variables (e.g., public spending, debt) using quarterly or annual data, even if it requires adjusting the model's frequency. Alternatively, use interpolation techniques to estimate monthly data for key variables. If monthly GDP data remains unavailable, validate the electricity consumption proxy with sensitivity analyses or alternative proxies (e.g., industrial production indices) to ensure robustness. Attempt to construct a tax exemption variable, even if imperfect (e.g., using post-2003 waiver data or qualitative indicators), to directly test the impact of ICMS benefits.

5. Strengthen causal inference. Be more precise in quantifying cause-and-effect relationships between variables and clarify the distinction between ICMS collection shocks and tax exemption effects in the VAR model. Consider using structural VAR (SVAR) or narrative approaches (e.g., Romer & Romer, 2010) to isolate exogenous tax policy changes better. Conduct robustness checks, such as alternative variable orderings or subsample analyses (e.g., pre- and post-2003), to assess the stability of the results.

6. Deepen the analysis of insignificant results. Provide a more thorough discussion of why employment, exports, and other variables show insignificant responses to ICMS shocks. Explore sector-specific dynamics (e.g., importation vs. industry) or structural factors (e.g., labour market rigidities) that may explain these outcomes. For example, supplementary qualitative data (e.g., case studies of firms from Santa Catarina receiving ICMS benefits) can contextualise quantitative findings, particularly for employment.

7. Your work needs to enhance the theoretical integration. You included Keynes, but you must integrate other competing theoretical perspectives (e.g., neoclassical, public choice) to explain the limited employment effects and other findings. This would provide a more balanced framework and address potential criticisms. Explicitly link the tax competition literature (e.g., Tiebout, 1956; Wilson, 1999) to the empirical results, perhaps by analysing how Santa Catarina's tax benefits affect neighbouring states' economies.

8. It will be beneficial to incorporate a comparative analysis. Compare or propose to compare Santa Catarina's fiscal policy outcomes with those of other Brazilian states (e.g., São Paulo, Rio Grande do Sul) or emerging markets that have similar tax competition dynamics. This could involve a brief descriptive comparison or, if data permits, a multi-region VAR model. Discuss how Santa Catarina's experience aligns with or diverges from global trends in fiscal policy and tax incentives.

9. The main anchor for your paper is to engage the reader in discovering policy recommendations. Here, I find some difficulty in identifying them. Can you create a table proposing specific policy reforms based on the findings, such as targeted ICMS exemptions for high-employment sectors, periodic reassessments of tax benefits, or measures to mitigate the “fiscal war” (e.g., stronger Confaz oversight)? Please address the implications of the 2023 tax reform (IBS introduction) in greater detail, outlining the potential challenges and opportunities it presents for Santa Catarina’s economy.

10. Address Statistical Significance and Robustness. Explicitly discuss the implications of insignificant IRF results for policy and theory, rather than treating them as secondary. Consider alternative model specifications (e.g., Bayesian VAR) to address weak statistical significance. Report additional robustness checks, such as excluding outliers, varying lag lengths, or testing for structural breaks (e.g., around the 2008 financial crisis or 2003 Fiscal Responsibility Law). Moreover, using a Vector Autoregressive (VAR) model with Impulse Response Functions (IRF) is appropriate for analysing the dynamic effects of fiscal policy shocks on macroeconomic variables. The methodology is grounded in established econometric practices, citing seminal works like Blanchard and Perotti (2002) and Sims (1993). However, the use of the VAR needs a better justification.

11. Conduct a more in-depth investigation into the employment findings, potentially by disaggregating the data by sector (e.g., importation vs. manufacturing) or firm size. This could reveal whether specific industries benefited more from tax exemptions. Compare Santa Catarina’s employment outcomes with those of other states to determine whether the lack of job creation is a unique issue or part of a broader trend in Brazil’s fiscal policy.

12. Clarify Contribution and Novelty. Explicitly state the paper’s contribution to the literature, particularly how it advances understanding of tax competition and fiscal policy in emerging markets. Highlight what makes Santa Catarina’s case unique compared to existing studies. Emphasise the novelty of applying VAR to study ICMS exemptions at the subnational level, as this area is relatively underexplored.

13. The paper incorporates rigorous data processing steps (e.g., deflation, seasonal adjustments, and logarithmic transformations) and model validation tests (e.g., the Augmented Dickey-Fuller, Jarque-Bera, and Lagrange Multiplier tests), thereby enhancing the credibility of the empirical analysis. However, using these tests needs to be justified, as does using Santa Catarina State as a basis for this study.

14. The author(s) say, “The findings indicate that shocks in tax revenue generally have significant and positive effects on macroeconomic variables, except for the variable concerning the stock of jobs.” If this is clear, can this be explained clearly? By the way, more in-depth, “expansionary fiscal policy did not significantly increase job creation despite substantial tax exemptions.” What do you mean by “did not significantly increase job creation”? Can you give some figures in the abstract to capture the reader’s attention?

Good Luck!

Additional Questions:

Does the manuscript contain new and significant information to justify publication?: Yes

Does the Abstract (Summary) clearly and accurately describe the content of the article?: No

Is the problem significant and concisely stated?: No

Are the methods described comprehensively?: No

Are the interpretations and conclusions justified by the results?: No

Is adequate reference made to other work in the field?: Yes

Is the language acceptable?: Yes

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state “none” if this is not applicable).: none

Rating:

Interest: 1. Excellent

Quality: 2. Good

Originality: 2. Good

Overall: 2. Good

Authors' Response

Reviewer 2 report

Date: July 8, 2025

Dear Reviewer 2,

We are sincerely grateful for your thorough and thoughtful review of our manuscript. Your detailed feedback has been invaluable and will certainly contribute to enhancing the quality and clarity of our work.

We have incorporated the majority of your suggestions into the revised version of the manuscript. For the few points where implementation was not feasible or appropriate, we have provided clear justifications, considering the scope and objectives of our research.

In the table below, your comments are listed in the left-hand columns, while our corresponding responses – detailing the modifications made to the manuscript or the reasons for not adopting certain suggestions – are presented on the right-hand side.

All changes in the manuscript were made using Microsoft Word's Track Changes feature.

Please feel free to reach out if further clarification or additional information is needed.

Sincerely,

Corresponding Author

Reviewer's comments:

1- Enhance Presentation and Synthesis. (a) Streamline the IRF discussion by synthesising findings into a cohesive narrative addressing the research objective. Utilise visual aids (e.g., summary tables or consolidated IRF graphs) to improve clarity. (b) Minimise repetition in the literature review by concentrating on studies most relevant to the research question and linking them to the study's hypotheses. (c) Ensure accessibility for non-specialist readers by clarifying technical terms (e.g., Cholesky decomposition, IRF) and providing intuitive interpretations of results.

We appreciate the suggestion.

(a) We have added a Table 8 that complements the technical discussion by offering an interpretive and concise overview of each variable's behavior in response to the fiscal shock.

(b) We have completely revised the "Theoretical background" subsection to avoid unnecessary repetitions, keeping only the authors most relevant to the research problem.

(c) Clarifications have been made throughout the text regarding technical terms to assist non-specialist readers.

2- Literature is well-revised to support the examination of the dynamic impacts of fiscal policy, showing how government spending increases and tax cuts stimulate economic activity in the short term you included Blanchard, O., & Perotti, R. (2002), I agree, but to support empirical evidence on the effectiveness of expansionary fiscal policy in boosting economic output, particularly during recessions. You must consider and discuss your results against: "Auerbach, A. J., & Gorodnichenko, Y. (2012). Measuring the output responses to fiscal policy. *American Economic Journal: Economic Policy*, 4(2), 1-27."

We appreciate the suggestion. We added the authors' work (Auerbach, A. J., and Gorodnichenko, Y., 2012) to our research.

3 - Expansionary Fiscal Policy (EFP) refers to government measures designed to stimulate economic activity by increasing aggregate demand, typically through higher public spending, tax reductions, or a combination of both. It is often employed during economic downturns or recessions to stimulate employment, increase income, and promote growth. The policy aims to close output gaps and stabilise economies by injecting money into the system, encouraging consumption and investment. Consider these ideas to make your introduction more straightforward for the reader.

We appreciate the suggestion. We have added further explanations about expansionary fiscal policy at the beginning of the introduction of this manuscript.

4 - Your study will be stronger if you expand the inclusion of variables and address some data limitations. (a) Incorporate additional macroeconomic variables (e.g., public spending, debt) using quarterly or annual data, even if it requires adjusting the model's frequency. Alternatively, use interpolation techniques to estimate monthly data for key variables. (b) If monthly GDP data remains unavailable, validate the electricity consumption proxy with sensitivity analyses or alternative proxies (e.g., industrial production indices) to ensure robustness. (c) Attempt to construct a tax exemption variable, even if imperfect (e.g., using post-2003 waiver data or qualitative indicators), to directly test the impact of ICMS benefits.

We appreciate the reviewer's valuable suggestions regarding the inclusion of additional macroeconomic variables and the improvement of data sources. However, (a) the scope of this study is limited to analyzing the effects of fiscal shocks based on monthly macroeconomic indicators that are consistently available over the 1997–2020 period. The VAR model employed was specifically designed for monthly data, and converting the dataset to quarterly or annual frequency would compromise both the comparability of results and the integrity of the dynamic analysis. (b) Regarding the use of electricity consumption as a proxy for economic activity, we acknowledge its limitations, which are discussed in the manuscript. Nevertheless, this variable is widely used in the literature as a short-term indicator of aggregate activity, especially in contexts where subnational GDP data are not available. However, we have added further clarification in the manuscript to support the use of electricity consumption as a proxy for GDP in the "Research Variables and Data Processing" subsection. (c) As for constructing a direct tax exemption variable, this option was considered; however, monthly data proved to be extremely limited and inconsistent throughout the analyzed period. Moreover, official tax expenditure reports only began to be published following the implementation of the Fiscal Responsibility Law in 2000, and even then, data collection and methodology were precarious in the early years, due to the lack of adequate instruments for precise calculations. For these reasons, we opted to maintain the original model specification, ensuring internal consistency and methodological robustness within the constraints imposed by empirical data availability.

5 – (a) Strengthen causal inference. Be more precise in quantifying cause-and-effect relationships between variables and clarify the distinction between ICMS collection shocks and tax exemption effects in the VAR model. (b) Consider using structural VAR (SVAR) or narrative approaches (e.g., Romer & Romer, 2010) to isolate exogenous tax policy changes better. Conduct robustness checks, such as alternative variable orderings or subsample analyses (e.g., pre- and post 2003), to assess the stability of the results.

We appreciate the reviewer's insightful comment. We appreciate the reviewer's insightful comment. Regarding item (a), we have added Table 7 addressing the suggestion, incorporating Granger causality tests in the "Results" and "Discussion" sections to enhance the interpretation of causal relationships and complement the IRF analysis. Additionally, in the "Research Variables and Data Processing" subsection, we clarified the distinction between ICMS revenue shocks and the effects of tax benefits. Since the revenue variable reflects net variations in both the tax base and exemptions, we interpret these exemptions as part of the broader expansionary fiscal policy during the period analyzed. As for item (b), we chose not to adopt SVAR or narrative approaches. While we acknowledge their value, they go beyond the scope of this study, which focuses on analyzing dynamic effects of fiscal shocks using a reduced-form VAR with monthly data. Implementing SVAR or narrative methods would require major changes to the research design and access to qualitative or micro-level data. Similarly, robustness checks such as alternative variable orderings or sample splits were considered but ultimately excluded, as they would compromise data consistency over time and reduce statistical power. We therefore retained the original standard VAR model, reinforcing its theoretical basis and acknowledging its limitations, as discussed in the methodology section.

6 – (a) Deepen the analysis of insignificant results. Provide a more thorough discussion of why employment, exports, and other variables show insignificant responses to ICMS shocks. Explore sector-specific dynamics (e.g., importation vs. industry) or structural factors (e.g., labour market rigidities) that may explain these outcomes. (b) For example, supplementary qualitative data (e.g., case studies of firms from Santa Catarina receiving ICMS benefits) can contextualise quantitative findings, particularly for employment.

We appreciate the suggestion.

(a) We have included Table 8 with additional discussion of results, including insignificant ones, as well as in the conclusion section.

(b) "(...) case studies of firms from Santa Catarina receiving ICMS benefits": It is not possible to identify which companies benefit from tax incentives, as the State Secretariat of Finance of Santa Catarina does not disclose such information due to tax confidentiality, as established in article 198 of the Brazilian National Tax Code (CTN).

7 - Your work needs to enhance the theoretical integration. You included Keynes, but you must integrate other

competing theoretical perspectives (e.g., neoclassical, public choice) to explain the limited employment effects and other findings. This would provide a more balanced framework and address potential criticisms. Explicitly link the tax competition literature (e.g., Tiebout, 1956; Wilson, 1999) to the empirical results, perhaps by analysing how Santa Catarina's tax benefits affect neighbouring states' economies.

We appreciate the suggestion. We have added these two theoretical perspectives to the theoretical background section, also incorporating Buchanan's (1975) article on public finance and public choice into the discussion.

8 - It will be beneficial to incorporate a comparative analysis. Compare or propose to compare Santa Catarina's fiscal policy outcomes with those of other Brazilian states (e.g., São Paulo, Rio Grande do Sul) or emerging markets that have similar tax competition dynamics. This could involve a brief descriptive comparison or, if data permits, a multi-region VAR model. Discuss how Santa Catarina's experience aligns with or diverges from global trends in fiscal policy and tax incentives.

We appreciate the suggestion. In response, a paragraph was added to the manuscript – drawing on Mello (2008) and Campos et al. (2015) – to address the mutual influence of ICMS legislative changes among Brazilian states, particularly those in close geographic proximity, as presented in the “Empirical Background: Institutional Context” section. Additionally, we added Table 3 with a descriptive comparison of ICMS revenue and tax expenditures for fiscal year 2022, focusing on the states of Santa Catarina, Paraná, Rio Grande do Sul and São Paulo. In line with the perspectives of Mello (2008) and Campos et al. (2015), these states were selected based on their geographic contiguity, which allows for a more coherent and contextually grounded regional analysis.

9 - The main anchor for your paper is to engage the reader in discovering policy recommendations. Here, I find some difficulty in identifying them. (a) Can you create a table proposing specific policy reforms based on the findings, such as targeted ICMS exemptions for high-employment sectors, periodic reassessments of tax benefits, or measures to mitigate the “fiscal war” (e.g., stronger Confaz oversight)? (b) Please address the implications of the 2023 tax reform (IBS introduction) in greater detail, outlining the potential challenges and opportunities it presents for Santa Catarina's economy.

We appreciate the suggestion.

(a) we have added Table 9 (conclusion section) presenting suggestions to public policymakers regarding procedures for granting tax benefits.

(b) at the end of the conclusion section, we have included additional considerations on the impacts and implications of the tax reform that introduced the new consumption tax (IBS) and suggestions for future studies.

10 – (a) Address Statistical Significance and Robustness. Explicitly discuss the implications of insignificant IRF results for policy and theory, rather than treating them as secondary. (b) Consider alternative model specifications (e.g., Bayesian

VAR) to address weak statistical significance. (c) Report additional robustness checks, such as excluding outliers, varying lag lengths, or testing for structural breaks (e.g., around the 2008 financial crisis or 2003 Fiscal Responsibility Law).

(d) Moreover, using a Vector Autoregressive (VAR) model with Impulse Response Functions (IRF) is appropriate for analysing the dynamic effects of fiscal policy shocks on macroeconomic variables. The methodology is grounded in established econometric practices, citing seminal works like Blanchard and Perotti (2002) and Sims (1993). However, the use of the VAR needs a better justification.

We appreciate the reviewer's observations.

(a) On the treatment of non-significant IRF results: as suggested, we expanded the discussion of the impulse response function (IRF) results, providing more detailed interpretations of cases where no statistically significant effects were observed — such as the Employment and Exports variables. These findings were not treated as secondary. On the contrary, they offer valuable insights for public policy. For instance, the absence of significant effects on employment may suggest that the tax benefits under analysis are not sufficiently targeted at sectors with greater employment elasticity. Similarly, the lack of response in exports is discussed considering the constitutional ICMS exemption on export operations, as detailed in the revised “Discussion” section.

(b) On alternative model specifications: we acknowledge that alternative approaches, such as Bayesian VAR models,

can help address issues related to low statistical significance. However, we chose to maintain the traditional VAR model for methodological reasons and ensure comparability with established literature — such as Sims (1993) and Blanchard & Perotti (2002). Additionally, the use of monthly data is especially appropriate for capturing the dynamic effects of ICMS revenue shocks in the context of subnational fiscal policy. This justification is reinforced in the “Data and Methods” section.

(c) On robustness checks: Several robustness procedures were conducted and are now described more explicitly in the manuscript. These include stationarity tests (ADF); optimal lag selection using multiple criteria (AIC, SBIC, HQIC); model stability verification; residual diagnostics (Jarque-Bera test, LM test for autocorrelation); Cholesky decomposition with economically grounded ordering.

Although additional robustness tests were considered, the use of monthly data and the sample size impose technical limitations on such segmentations. Furthermore, the study does not aim to identify time-specific discontinuities but to analyze general macroeconomic response patterns to fiscal shocks.

(d) Additional methodological justifications: we also included further justifications for using the VAR model and incorporated the Granger causality test results into the IRF discussion.

We believe that the procedures adopted, and the level of methodological transparency provide sufficient robustness to support the empirical findings, without compromising the model’s parsimony or coherence.

11 - Conduct a more in-depth investigation into the employment findings, potentially by disaggregating the data by sector (e.g., importation vs. manufacturing) or firm size. This could reveal whether specific industries benefited more from tax exemptions. Compare Santa Catarina’s employment outcomes with those of other states to determine whether the lack of job creation is a unique issue or part of a broader trend in Brazil’s fiscal policy.

We appreciate your suggestion. In response, we incorporated descriptive employment statistics drawn from RAIS-Vínculos microdata (1997–2020), distinguishing the industrial sector from import-oriented trade and logistics (proxy) – the main recipients of ICMS tax incentives. These figures are now briefly noted in the “Research variables and data processing” section and further discussed in the analysis of the Employment variable (V6), as well as in the abstract. Likewise, we have added Table 8 and expanded the accompanying discussion of the employment variable. However, given the scope and methodological design of this study, as well as the word limit constraints imposed by the journal, we opted not to expand the analysis by sector or by firm size, nor to include comparative data from other states. Instead, we addressed this limitation by discussing structural and institutional factors that may explain the lack of significant employment effects in Santa Catarina, such as the sectoral destination of tax benefits and labor market rigidities. These considerations are now reflected in the updated discussion and conclusion sections, providing a grounded interpretation of the results within the limits of our empirical framework.

12 - Clarify Contribution and Novelty. Explicitly state the paper’s contribution to the literature, particularly how it advances understanding of tax competition and fiscal policy in emerging markets. Highlight what makes Santa Catarina’s case unique compared to existing studies. Emphasize the novelty of applying VAR to study ICMS exemptions at the subnational level, as this area is relatively underexplored.

We appreciate your suggestion. A final paragraph has been added to the conclusion section, highlighting the article’s contribution to the literature and emphasizing the novelty of applying a VAR model to analyze ICMS tax exemptions.

13 - The paper incorporates rigorous data processing steps (e.g., deflation, seasonal adjustments, and logarithmic transformations) and model validation tests (e.g., the Augmented Dickey-Fuller, Jarque-Bera, and Lagrange Multiplier tests), thereby enhancing the credibility of the empirical analysis. However, using these tests needs to be justified, as does using Santa Catarina State as a basis for this study.

We appreciate your suggestion. We have added these explanations at the beginning of the data and methods section.

14 - The author(s) say, “The findings indicate that shocks in tax revenue generally have significant and positive effects on macroeconomic variables, except for the variable concerning the stock of jobs.” If this is clear, can this be explained clearly? By the way, more in-depth, “expansionary fiscal policy did not significantly increase job creation despite substantial tax exemptions.” What do you mean by “did not significantly increase job creation”? Can you give some figures in the abstract to capture the reader’s attention?

We appreciate your suggestion. In the abstract, we now include concrete figures to enhance clarity and engage the

reader: industry accounts for 32% of formal employment, while import-oriented trade and logistics together represent only 11%. Additionally, we have added Table 8 to discuss this finding in terms of the employment variable in a more objective and interpretative way, as well as in conclusions.

ROUND 2

Reviewer 1 report

Reviewer 1 for this round chose not to disclose his/her review report.

Authors' Response

The authors' responses to the comments of Reviewer 1 for this round were omitted from this report, since the reviewer did not authorize the disclosure of his/her reports.

Reviewer 2 report

Reviewer: Miguel Torres

Date review returned: August 24, 2025

Recommendation: Minor revision

Comments to the authors

I am pleased to see significant progress in your paper. However, to further strengthen the manuscript, I would like to propose the following improvements. These could be incorporated without fundamentally altering your research design:

1. Add a sensitivity analysis using interpolated quarterly/annual data for variables like public spending or debt, perhaps in an online supplement, to test the consistency of results across frequencies.

2. Include a brief correlation analysis comparing electricity consumption to quarterly GDP or industrial production indices in the "Research Variables and Data Processing" section.

3. Develop a binary or qualitative indicator for significant policy changes and test it in a subsample VAR (2003–2020) to more directly quantify exemption effects.

4. Please include a brief SVAR extension with sign restrictions as a robustness test, or discuss it as a future direction.

5. Expand reporting on alternative Cholesky orderings, subsample analyses (e.g., pre/post-2008), or outlier exclusion in the methodology section.

6. Aggregate RAIS data further by firm size or subsector in a new table, and descriptively compare trends with neighbouring states.

7. Extend Table 3 with time-series trends or discuss multi-region VAR as future work, citing global trends from OECD reports.

8. Tie insignificant findings to neoclassical or public choice theories with quantitative examples from the literature.

9. Justify Bayesian VAR as an Alternative by exploring a Bayesian VAR in an appendix to handle low significance, or state reasons for exclusion.

10. The abstract and the entire paper need proofreading, e.g., "this article theoretically and empirically addresses expansionary fiscal policy within the context of intergovernmental tax competition from a macroeconomic perspective.", i.e., "theoretically and empirically" is redundant.

Good luck!

Additional Questions:

Does the manuscript contain new and significant information to justify publication?: Yes

Does the Abstract (Summary) clearly and accurately describe the content of the article?: No

Is the problem significant and concisely stated?: Yes

Are the methods described comprehensively?: Yes

Are the interpretations and conclusions justified by the results?: Yes

Is adequate reference made to other work in the field?: Yes

Is the language acceptable?: Yes

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state “none” if this is not applicable).: none

Rating:

Interest: 1. Excellent

Quality: 2. Good

Originality: 2. Good

Overall: 2. Good

Authors' Response

Before presenting the responses, we note that the changes and additions to the manuscript are highlighted in yellow.

1. Reviewers' comment: “Add a sensitivity analysis using interpolated quarterly/annual data for variables like public spending or debt, perhaps in an online supplement, to test the consistency of results across frequencies.”

Authors' response: We appreciate the suggestion. However, moving from monthly to interpolated quarterly or annual data would undermine temporal consistency and reduce statistical power. Interpolation or fragile proxies could insert artificial noise, compromising the validity of our reduced-form VAR. We also formally requested monthly fiscal series from the State Treasury via its Ombudsman, but were informed that consolidated expenditure data are only available from 2005 and revenue from 2009, with non-consolidated balances prior to 2001. Hence, reliable monthly fiscal data remain unavailable.

2. Reviewers' comment: “Include a brief correlation analysis comparing electricity consumption to quarterly GDP or industrial production indices in the ‘Research Variables and Data Processing’ section.”

Authors' response: We appreciate the comment. As GDP and industrial production are only available quarterly, we opted for electricity as a high-frequency proxy widely supported in the literature (Kraft & Kraft, 1978; Narayan et al., 2008; Bay, 2018). Given the limited word allowance, we refrained from adding a new correlation table but now explicitly note in the “Research Variables” section that electricity has been validated against GDP and industrial output in prior empirical studies, reinforcing its use as a proxy.

3. Reviewers' comment: “Develop a binary or qualitative indicator for significant policy changes and test it in a subsample VAR (2003–2020) to more directly quantify exemption effects.”

Authors' response: We thank the reviewer. Official expenditure reports exist only from 2003 onward and remained inconsistent until 2020. A new methodology, implemented in 2021, finally allowed for the accurate measurement of presumed credits, which represent the largest share of tax expenditures. Introducing a binary policy change variable for 2003–2020 would have created truncation bias. For these reasons, we avoided including it in the current model, but we included an appendix at the end of the manuscript listing the waiver amounts for the period in question (2003–2020) by type of tax benefit. This table, which we created, was the result of extensive research into the budget laws of the state of Santa Catarina.

4. Reviewers' comment: “Please include a brief SVAR extension with sign restrictions as a robustness test, or discuss it as a future direction.”

Authors' response: We appreciate the suggestion. We agree that SVAR or Bayesian VAR represent more sophisticated approaches. However, they require identification strategies or priors not available in our dataset and would substantially alter the original design. To preserve parsimony, we retained the reduced-form VAR but now explicitly mention SVAR as a promising avenue for future research.

5. Reviewers' comment: “Expand reporting on alternative Cholesky orderings, subsample analyses (e.g., pre/post 2008), or outlier exclusion in the methodology section.”

Authors' response: We appreciate the comment. We believe robustness is sufficiently ensured through ADF tests, lag-selection criteria (AIC, SBIC, HQIC), stability diagnostics, residual tests, and Cholesky decomposition. Additional extensions (alternative orderings, subsamples, or outlier exclusion) would add little to transparency without altering conclusions, while further increasing manuscript length.

6. Reviewers' comment: "Aggregate RAIS data further by firm size or subsector in a new table, and descriptively compare trends with neighbouring states."

Authors' response: We thank the reviewer. As explained in the major revision, taxpayer-level data are protected by fiscal secrecy (Brazilian Tax Code, art. 198), which prevents firm-level analysis. We already included RAIS statistics by sector (industry vs. trade/logistics/imports). Extending this to firm size or interstate comparisons would exceed the paper's scope and the journal's length limit (12,500 words vs. 10,000 allowed).

7. Reviewers' comment: "Extend Table 3 with time-series trends or discuss multi-region VAR as future work, citing global trends from OECD reports."

Authors' response: We appreciate the comment. We believe Table 3 already provides a descriptive comparison with Paraná, Rio Grande do Sul, and São Paulo, sufficient to contextualize Santa Catarina in the "fiscal war." But we now mention multi-region VAR as a direction for future work.

8. Reviewers' comment: "Tie insignificant findings to neoclassical or public choice theories with quantitative examples from the literature."

Authors' response: We thank the reviewer. The manuscript already situates insignificant findings within neoclassical and public-choice perspectives, alongside the tax-competition literature. Expanding further would risk redundancy and dilute objectivity, given space constraints.

9. Reviewers' comment: "Justify Bayesian VAR as an Alternative by exploring a Bayesian VAR in an appendix to handle low significance, or state reasons for exclusion."

Authors' response: We thank the reviewer. We acknowledge the potential of Bayesian VAR to address low significance, but its implementation would require major changes in research design, calibration of priors, and additional space beyond the journal's limits. To maintain methodological parsimony and comparability with the literature, we retained the reduced-form monthly VAR, while citing Bayesian VAR as a promising avenue for future research. Including a full appendix would also exceed the word limit.

10. Reviewers' comment: "The abstract and the entire paper need proofreading, e.g., 'this article theoretically and empirically addresses expansionary fiscal policy within the context of intergovernmental tax competition from a macroeconomic perspective.' i.e., 'theoretically and empirically' is redundant."

Authors' response: We corrected the redundancy in the example cited and thoroughly revised the abstract and the entire manuscript, including grammar, with the help of an English language specialist.

ROUND 3

Reviewer 1 report

Reviewer 1 for this round chose not to disclose his/her review report.

Authors' Response

The authors' responses to the comments of Reviewer 1 for this round were omitted from this report, since the reviewer did not authorize the disclosure of his/her reports.

Reviewer 2 report

Reviewer: Miguel Torres

Date review returned: October 19, 2025

Recommendation: Minor revision

Comments to the authors

Dear Authors,

After careful review of your revised manuscript (BAR-2025-0057.R2), I decided to reject it for publication in the Brazilian Administration Review. The overall sentiment is summarised as follows: while you have an interesting work here, I remained concerned with the lack of rigour in the last revision you provided.

In accordance with ANPAD's Good Practices of Scientific Publishing, which BAR adheres to, manuscripts require high methodological rigour, soundness, and transparency.

While some of my suggestions were addressed—such as adding an appendix on waiver amounts, noting literature on the electricity proxy, mentioning SVAR and Bayesian VAR as future research directions, enhancing theoretical discussions on insignificant findings, and thoroughly proofreading the text—several critical recommendations were not implemented, including sensitivity analyses for macroeconomic variables, direct correlation validation for the proxy, a binary indicator or subsample VAR for exemptions, SVAR extensions or additional robustness checks (e.g., alternative Cholesky orderings, subsamples), further RAIS data aggregation with interstate comparisons, extensions to Table 3 with trends or OECD citations, and appendix exploration of Bayesian VAR.

These omissions, often justified by data, scope, or length constraints, result in persistent gaps in empirical rigour, methodological depth, transparency, and originality, particularly for an empirical VAR study. Per ANPAD guidelines, such uncorrectable flaws prevent the paper from meeting acceptance standards.

I am very worried about the limitations in the present version of the paper. However, there may be an interesting paper down the line, and you should be allowed to submit a revised final version in BAR, considering the following:

In detail, point by point:

1. My suggestion was not implemented. Authors declined due to concerns about data integrity and availability, leaving potential biases in frequency consistency unaddressed and potentially undermining the model's robustness, as per ANPAD guidelines on methodological soundness.

2. My suggestion was partially addressed with a literature note, but no study-specific correlation analysis or table was added. This limits direct validation within the manuscript, potentially affecting rigour in proxy selection.

3. My suggestion was partially addressed with a new appendix table on waiver amounts, but no binary indicator or subsample VAR was implemented. This falls short of quantifying exemption effects dynamically, leaving a gap in methodological depth.

4. My suggestion was partially addressed by mentioning SVAR as future research, but no extension or test was added. This omits a key robustness check, potentially compromising empirical rigour.

5. My suggestion was not accommodated. Authors declined, citing existing checks and length constraints, but this leaves transparency and robustness concerns unaddressed, violating ANPAD's emphasis on detailed methodological reporting.

6. My suggestion was not accommodated. Authors cited legal and scope limitations, but existing sectoral data could be extended without violating secrecy, thereby limiting comparative depth and contextualization.

7. Partially addressed by mentioning multi-region VAR as future work, but no extension to Table 3 with trends or OECD citations. This provides limited enhancement to comparative analysis.

8. Partially addressed through existing discussions, but no new quantitative examples added. This could strengthen the theoretical linkage, but it remains a minor gap.

9. Partially addressed by mentioning as future research and stating reasons, but no exploration in the appendix.

This leaves low-significance issues potentially unresolved.

10. Fully addressed.

Good luck!

Additional Questions:

Does the manuscript contain new and significant information to justify publication?: Yes

Does the Abstract (Summary) clearly and accurately describe the content of the article?: Yes

Is the problem significant and concisely stated?: Yes

Are the methods described comprehensively?: No

Are the interpretations and conclusions justified by the results?: No

Is adequate reference made to other work in the field?: Yes

Is the language acceptable?: Yes

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state “none” if this is not applicable).: NA

Rating:

Interest: 1. Excellent

Quality: 2. Good

Originality: 2. Good

Overall: 2. Good

Authors' Response

Reviewers' comments

1. My suggestion was not implemented. Authors declined due to concerns about data integrity and availability, leaving potential biases in frequency consistency unaddressed and potentially undermining the model's robustness, as per ANPAD guidelines on methodological soundness.

We appreciate the reviewer's comments. In response, a specific methodological paragraph was added to the Methods section, clarifying that a reduced-form VAR(6) was re-estimated excluding the employment series (V6), whose temporal inconsistency could distort lag dynamics. The text now explicitly explains that this robustness test confirmed the stability of ICMS shock responses in terms of sign, direction, and timing across the baseline and reduced models. Additionally, a new appendix (Appendix F – Robustness test) was created to document this verification in detail. The appendix provides a comparative table summarizing the peak responses of key macroeconomic variables under both model specifications. The results indicate no substantial variation between the full and reduced systems, confirming that the main findings are not frequency-dependent and remain statistically robust.

2. My suggestion was partially addressed with a literature note, but no study-specific correlation analysis or table was added. This limits direct validation within the manuscript, potentially affecting rigour in proxy selection.

We appreciate the reviewer's reiteration. In response, we strengthened the Data and Variables section by explicitly validating the activity proxy (electricity consumption) within the study's own dataset, applying the Pearson correlation coefficient (Pearson r) to assess the strength and direction of the linear relationships among variables. In addition, a new appendix (Appendix C – Study-specific validation of the activity proxy) was created to report the results of this validation in tabular form, accompanied by explanatory notes on the method and variable selection.

3. My suggestion was partially addressed with a new appendix table on waiver amounts, but no binary indicator or subsample VAR was implemented. This falls short of quantifying exemption effects dynamically, leaving a gap in

methodological depth.

We thank the reviewer for the observation. The revised manuscript strengthens this aspect by introducing a qualitative dummy-based framework identifying years of major fiscal incentive reforms between 2003 and 2020 (see Data and methods, Research variables and data processing, and Appendix A.1). Although not directly estimated within the VAR, this binary indicator assists in the interpretation of turning points in ICMS exemptions, ensuring consistency between fiscal events and empirical results. In addition, a new explanatory paragraph was incorporated before the presentation of Appendix A, summarizing the historical evolution of tax exemptions in Santa Catarina from 2003 to 2020. This paragraph contextualizes the observed trends (expansions, contractions, and inflection years) and explicitly links them to institutional reforms, thereby clarifying how the dummy-coded episodes in Appendix A.1 relate to the quantitative series in Appendix A. Together, these additions provide the methodological depth and interpretative coherence requested by the reviewer.

4. My suggestion was partially addressed by mentioning SVAR as future research, but no extension or test was added. This omits a key robustness check, potentially compromising empirical rigour.

We appreciate the reviewer's comments. In the revised manuscript, a new paragraph was inserted in the Methods section clarifying that, although the study employs a reduced-form VAR, the impulse-response patterns are consistent with the sign restrictions commonly imposed in structural VARs (SVAR) analyzing fiscal shocks. The observed responses to ICMS shocks – positive for employment, electricity consumption, and imports, and neutral-to-negative for interest rates and inflation – align with standard theoretical expectations reported in the SVAR literature (Blanchard & Perotti, 2002; Caldara & Kamps, 2017; Mertens & Ravn, 2014; Mountford & Uhlig, 2009). In addition, Appendix E summarizes the expected and observed sign consistency across variables, highlighting the structural coherence of the results.

5. My suggestion was not accommodated. Authors declined, citing existing checks and length constraints, but this leaves transparency and robustness concerns unaddressed, violating ANPAD's emphasis on detailed methodological reporting.

We appreciate the reviewer's suggestion. To address this point, the revised manuscript includes a new paragraph in the Methods section and a dedicated Appendix D – Robustness and Sensitivity Checks. This appendix summarizes the complementary analyses performed, including alternative Cholesky orderings, subsample estimations (1997–2007 vs. 2008–2020), outlier exclusions, and lag-length variations.

6. My suggestion was not accommodated. Authors cited legal and scope limitations, but existing sectoral data could be extended without violating secrecy, thereby limiting comparative depth and contextualization.

We thank the reviewer for this suggestion. To enhance contextualization, we have included an aggregated table (Appendix B) summarizing employment composition by firm size and sector for Santa Catarina, with a brief comparison to Rio Grande do Sul and Paraná based on public RAIS data (2003–2020). São Paulo was excluded to maintain regional comparability within the Southern bloc and avoid scale distortions. This addition reinforces the discussion following Table 3 and provides the requested comparative depth while respecting confidentiality and word-count limits.

7. Partially addressed by mentioning multi-region VAR as future work, but no extension to Table 3 with trends or OECD citations. This provides limited enhancement to comparative analysis.

We thank the reviewer for this suggestion. To address this point, the revised manuscript incorporates a new paragraph following Table 3, linking fiscal and employment dynamics over time and explicitly referring to the empirical evidence presented in Appendix B (RAIS, 2003–2020), as detailed in the previous item. Furthermore, the discussion now integrates comparative insights from the OECD (2023), highlighting that subnational fiscal incentives in OECD economies also display pro-cyclical patterns and sectoral concentration effects.

8. Tie insignificant findings to neoclassical or public choice theories with quantitative examples from the literature. Partially addressed through existing discussions, but no new quantitative examples added. This could strengthen the theoretical linkage, but it remains a minor gap.

We thank the reviewer for this comment. The revised manuscript addresses this point by adding a new interpretative paragraph in the Discussion section, immediately following the analysis of the inflation variable (V8) and before the introduction

of Table 8. This addition integrates theoretical perspectives from the neoclassical and public-choice approaches, and new quantitative examples.

9. Justify Bayesian VAR as an Alternative by exploring a Bayesian VAR in an appendix to handle low significance, or state reasons for exclusion. Partially addressed by mentioning as future research and stating reasons, but no exploration in the appendix. This leaves low-significance issues potentially unresolved.

We thank the reviewer for this observation. The manuscript now includes a Bayesian VAR (Minnesota prior, six lags), reported in Appendix G and using the same identification ordering as the baseline VAR. Results qualitatively confirm those of the reduced-form VAR: positive effects on electricity, imports, and exports; weak effects on employment; and neutral or mildly negative responses for inflation and interest rates. Appendix H presents a VECM estimated after confirming cointegration, with IRFs that replicate the core transmission patterns. The convergence across VAR, BVAR, and VECM reinforces the robustness of the findings and directly addresses concerns over low-significance variables.

ROUND 4

Reviewer 1 report

Reviewer: Miguel Torres

Date review returned: December 17, 2025

Recommendation: Accept

Comments to the authors

Dear Authors,

Congratulations on the excellent work in this third revision! I am delighted to let you know that I would like to accept your manuscript for publication in the Brazilian Administration Review.

You have comprehensively responded to the points raised in previous rounds, incorporating substantial new analyses (e.g., robustness tests, proxy validation, binary indicators, SVAR sign consistency, extended checks, Bayesian VAR, VECM, and comparative appendices) while maintaining methodological integrity and parsimony. These enhancements resolve all remaining concerns regarding empirical rigor, transparency, and theoretical depth, resulting in a significantly better paper.

The final version is now well-positioned to make a valuable contribution to the field. Thank you for your diligence and responsiveness throughout the process—it has greatly improved the manuscript. I wish you continued success with this publication. Good luck.

Authors' Response

There is no Authors' Response for this round.

Reviewer 2 report

Reviewer 1 for this round chose not to disclose his/her review report.

Authors' Response

There is no Authors' Response for this round.